

Enterprise Social Networks: Overcoming Data Protection and Implementation Challenges

Ammar JAMAL ^{a*}

^a Faculty of Management, Comenius University, Bratislava, Slovakia

Abstract

In an increasingly digitalized business environment, the implementation of Enterprise Social Networks (ESN) has become a crucial factor for improving communication, collaboration and innovation within organizations. However, beyond the potential benefits, the implementation of such systems poses significant challenges, particularly in terms of data protection and regulatory compliance, such as compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). While ESN offer new opportunities for operational efficiency, their successful implementation requires a careful consideration of technical and organizational factors. This article examines the interface between ESN implementation and data protection, drawing on expert opinions and existing literature. It explores the complexity of ESN adoption in organizations, where technical and cultural dimensions must be carefully aligned to ensure both data protection compliance and a smooth organizational adoption. The article also presents various technical solution scenarios to address data protection challenges and highlights the need for a multi-dimensional approach to overcome technical and emotional obstacles in the implementation process. By exploring these aspects, this article contributes to a broader discussion on how organizations can effectively implement ESN while preserving data protection to successfully position themselves as modern, agile organizations in a digitalized world.

Keywords: Enterprise Social Networks (ESN), Data Protection, GDPR, Collaboration, Digital Transformation, Technical and Organizational Challenges, Compliance

Article Classification: Viewpoint

1 Introduction

Social networking sites first emerged in the 1990s. An early example of these websites is Theglobe.com, founded in 1995. Companies quickly realized that social networks could offer a fast and efficient marketing method. Social media is a great way for companies to reach their customers and help their business grow (Fürst, 2024). In 2005, as social networking became more popular, Myspace had more page views than Google. Myspace was followed by Facebook in 2004, which by 2010 already had over 500 million active users and in 2024 had 3 billion

* Corresponding author: Ammar JAMAL, Faculty of Management, Comenius University in Bratislava, Odbojárov 10, 820 05 Bratislava 25, Slovakia, email: jamal2@uniba.sk

active users. This means that one in three people worldwide are Facebook users. From its beginning, Facebook's growth was a boom in the social networking space (Hinchcliffe, 2012).

This was followed by Instagram and Twitter (X). In 2010, there were reportedly more than 200 social networking sites on the Internet. In the years that followed, purely business-related sites also followed, such as Open Business Club, Xing and Linked in. Since 2020, company-owned platforms have also existed that, in addition to employees, also provide access to selected people (universities, business partners, etc.) and allow information exchange (TÜV Nord, 2024).

Data protection is more important than ever in times of advancing digitization and the multiple relocation of the workplace to the home office. Not only because there are corresponding legal obligations – the protection of the data of your employees, contractual partners and customers is in your own interest. On the one hand, this allows you to fulfil large parts of your compliance obligations and thus avoid fines or claims for damages. On the other hand, managers create trust in your company and in your products or services.

As the use of Enterprise Social Networking Systems (ESN) in business becomes more popular, the specific challenge of the implementation and usage of ESN and the requirements of data protection need to be addressed (Lackes, 2019).

This point of view offers insights in these challenges as well as suggestions regarding technical solutions.

2 Research Methodology

To explore the issues and solutions related to the implementation of Enterprise Social Networks (ESN) in compliance with data protection regulations, in particular the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), this point of view uses a qualitative approach focused on expert opinions. Focusing on the insights of professionals with practical experience in ESN usage and its management and data protection, this approach aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current challenges faced by organizations regarding ESN and data protection. This expert-led methodology provides practical, experience-based insights that complement the theoretical discourse on ESN and data protection.

2.1 Questionnaire and participants

For the expert interviews, a questionnaire with ten qualitative questions was developed. The content focused on examining the challenges and possible solutions in the use and implementation of Enterprise Social Networks (ESN) in the context of data protection requirements. The structure of the questionnaire is as follows:

1. General use of ESN
2. Data protection requirements
3. Implementation challenges
4. Data management and security
5. Roles of data protection officers (DPOs)
6. Training
7. Technical data protection measures
8. Organizational best practices
9. Ethical considerations
10. Future challenges

The experts have been recruited via the personal network of the author. As the experts were selected manually and approached personally, the response rate was 100%. Due to

limitations regarding time, the number of experts that were contacted was limited to 10. The respondents are employees of middle sized to large enterprises. Although the overall number of respondents is limited, based on the nature of this article as a point of view, the author is of the opinion that the results are representative and valuable. They provide a basis for further, more intense examination.

3 Definitions

3.1 Enterprise Social Networking Systems (ESN)

ESN are online platforms designed to facilitate communication, collaboration and knowledge sharing between employees within a company. They enable employees to network with each other, exchange information and ideas, collaborate on projects and build social networks within the company. They support a variety of business functions including project management, team collaboration, innovation and employee engagement. Their advantage is that they connect employees across different locations, time zones and departments, making collaboration and information exchange easier (Schleuter, 2019).

Figure 1 Challenges of Usage and Implementation of Enterprise Social Networks (Digital Adoption Team, 2024)

3.2 Data Protection

Depending on the perspective, data protection is understood as protection against abusive data processing, protection of the right to informational self-determination, protection of personal rights in data processing and also protection of privacy. Data protection is a right that every person can decide for themselves who should have access to which of their personal data and when. The essence of such data protection laws is that the power imbalance between

organizations and individuals can be balanced under certain conditions. Data protection is intended to counteract the tendency towards transparent people, the escalation of state surveillance measures (surveillance state) and data monopolies of private companies in the diversely digital and networked information society (Berwanger, 2024).

3.3 Data Protection Officer

A corporate data protection officer (DPO) has an important and responsible role under the EU GDPR. Working at the interface between companies, data protection authorities and data subjects, the DPO has the necessary data protection expertise in the companies to design, control and communicate the implementation of data protection requirements. This also includes watching over the implementation and usage of ESN regarding data handling (Siepermann, 2024).

In companies, both an internal and an external data protection officer can be appointed: While an internal DPO is a regular employee of the company, an external DPO is commissioned as part of a service relationship.

A data protection officer is an expert in data protection. In particular, she has the task of ensuring the implementation of the requirements of the GDPR and other data protection regulations in a company and preventing data protection violations. She is also considered an intermediary between companies, affected parties and supervisory authorities (Lackes, 2019).

One of the tasks of a DPO is to contribute to a data security strategy. The Data Security Officer is primarily responsible for the data security strategy (Pratt, 2022).

Figure 2 Components of a data security strategy (Pratt, 2022)

4 Legal and ethical requirements

4.1 General Data Protection Regulation

Building on the Basic Law (GG), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has been in force in Germany since 2018, which standardizes the rules for the processing of personal data by most controllers, both private and public, throughout the EU (Schiller, 2019). However, the data protection regime of GDPR offers also possibilities for data mining for research and for business purposes without jeopardizing the data protection rights of the data subjects (Comandè et al., 2022). The GDPR consists of 99 articles in 11 chapters (Intersoft Consulting, 2024).

4.2 Principles of personal data processing

The GDPR explicitly lists the following six principles for the processing of personal data in Art. 5 (Intersoft Consulting, 2024):

- Lawfulness, fair processing, transparency
- Purpose limitation (processing only for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes)
- Data minimisation ('appropriate and significant for the purpose and adapted to the [...] necessary measure')
- Accuracy ('all reasonable steps must be taken to ensure that [inaccurate] personal data is deleted or rectified without undue delay')
- Storage limitation (data must be stored 'in a form that allows the identification of data subjects only for as long as [...] is required')
- Integrity and confidentiality ('adequate security of personal data [...], including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or harm')

The controller must demonstrate compliance with all these principles. Failure to comply with these principles and accountability may result in an appropriate fine of up to €20 million or, in the case of a company, up to 4% of its total annual global turnover.

4.3 Ethical principles

Compliance with ethical principles is a principle of human action, which precedes as well as after the legal requirements. This is always a voluntary commitment to ethical integrity, which is reflected in every facet of the work environment. Data management in ESN also need to follow ethical standards (Javan, 2024).

Important findings are:

- The ethical role is crucial for trust in an organization.
- Data protection ethics are a central aspect for compliance standards.
- Internal and external data protection officers help to avoid conflicts of interest in companies.
- Transparency and open communication shape the ethical foundations of our work.
- Safeguarding the rights of data subjects is at the heart of our ethical responsibility.

Figure 4 Ethical Considerations in Data Collection (Jayan, 2024)

4.4 Privacy challenges

Data protection in general has become an intensively discussed topic, not least due to the GDPR, and is currently enjoying special attention in companies. The threat to internal systems

from attacks carried out via the Internet is also perceived by companies as a more significant risk than in the past (Turban, 2024). The de facto connection between a moderation platform running on the Internet and an ESN entails corresponding risks, which can lead to extensive discussion in the implementation project.

Important topics are:

- Emergence of a gateway and technical safety concerns. The moderation system located on the Internet accesses the content of the internal social community. Accordingly, there is a risk of external attacks. In order to make the system more secure at this stage, interfaces and the system itself must be ‘hardened’, an effort that is usually not provided for a community of practice that actually runs internally (Saint-Onge, 2012).
- Outflow of information from internal to external. The basic character of an internal social network is the discussion of sensitive and/or internal topics. Accordingly, it is viewed critically if content from this community is available directly via a tool on the Internet or if only availability via the Internet would be conceivable. The value of an ESN community is reduced if there is unauthorized access and visibility of the content for third parties on the Internet, even if not factually but only unconsciously perceived or assumed (Chen, 2022). As a result, there is a risk that employees will not freely exchange their opinions but will feel restricted in their ability to express themselves. A merely perceived threat of an innovation in the technical system has a psychological-cultural dimension that must be taken into account (Elison, 2015).
- Risk of breach of data protection regulations. The posts of an ESN may also contain personal data, such as the name or user ID. This content must not be accessible to third parties via the Internet.

5 Results

The results of the survey will be presented in the order of the questionnaire. For a comprehensive presentation, the results for each question were consolidated and summarized.

5.1 General use of ESN

All companies surveyed started introducing and using ESN more than 5 years ago. The main objectives are to support internal communication and collaboration. Popular platforms include Microsoft Teams, Yammer and Slack. They are used for project management, knowledge management and to clarify organizational issues (e.g. coordination of daily work priorities). Three companies use solutions developed internally; those are accessible via the intranet.

5.2 Data protection requirements

The vast majority of companies (7 out of 10) reported having specific privacy policies for the use of ESN. These are GDPR compliant. The guidelines regulate which data can be processed on the platforms and which data can only be processed or shared with explicit consent. Three companies are currently reviewing their policies due to new requirements.

5.3 Implementation challenges

All companies reported initial difficulties in ensuring GDPR compliance. The difficulties of integrating ESN into existing IT infrastructures were particularly highlighted. It also took a long time to raise awareness among employees about data protection risks.

Furthermore, the management of access rights was mentioned as a critical point, as it is often necessary to implement the need-to-know principle and departments often have different data requirements.

5.4 Data management and security

All companies have implemented measures to protect personal data, including encryption, two-factor authentication and strict access controls.

5.5 Roles of data protection officers (DPOs)

In 5 out of 10 companies, an internal DPO oversees the use of ESN and GDPR compliance. Other companies rely on external data protection officers who work closely with legal and IT departments to ensure compliance. The DPO is usually also responsible for employee training. Those findings are in line with professional standards for DPO of EU (European Commission 45/2001)

5.6 Training and awareness of employees

All companies have training programs in place to regularly inform employees about data protection issues. Most undergo annual training. For most companies, data protection training takes place during onboarding. Employees receive training on how to identify sensitive data and communicate securely on ESN.

5.7 Technical data protection measures

The most common technical measures include end-to-end encryption, regular backups, and automatic data deletion processes for information that is outdated or no longer needed. Some companies rely on anonymization processes for sensitive data. Some encryption techniques are fully in line with GDPR (Spindler, 2016).

5.8 Organizational best practices

Companies have developed several best practices to ensure that their use of ESN complies with data protection regulations. These include guidelines for handling sensitive information, periodic data protection reviews, and the application of access restrictions for certain services. In cases where file repositories are shared with external business partners or clients, an automatic reminder is periodically sent to the file repository owners asking them to check whether the shares are still necessary.

5.9 Ethical considerations

All companies implement legal and ethical requirements. Great importance is attached to the protection of employee privacy. Trust in internal communication is also crucial. Companies have established clear communication rules to prevent employees from inadvertently sharing personal or confidential information. These ethical issues correspond to known findings (Schoentgen, 2021).

5.10 Future challenges

Often mentioned challenges are the increasing complexity of data protection requirements, the integration of modern analytics tools supported by artificial intelligence, the use of workstations outside the office. New working models bring new data protection risks. These findings also correspond to current literature (Keber, 2023).

6 Developed solution scenarios with regard to data protection

Even if the actual decision-making process in the company is complex, emotional and political, at least basic solution scenarios can be defined to provide guidance. In this section, different solution scenarios are presented. As a limiting factor, in this article, the author focuses on technical solution scenarios.

6.1 General measures

With regard to the technical hazard, measures must be taken to adequately secure the interface between the Internet and the company's intranet. In addition, there is the possibility of technical protection of the internal social community with the usual procedures. However, this will not be considered further here, as the situation considered in the application case represents a more complex problem case due to the opening to the 'outside' that could not be solved with the usual measures. The following possible solutions should therefore be considered for the use case (Leonardi, 2024; Kiron, 2012).

6.2 Intermediate Platform

This makes it possible to push only certain content into an intermediate platform and to allow the moderation software to access only this so called 'proxy system'. It would be possible to keep content temporarily available (vs. persistence data storage). However, this solution only prevents read access by the external moderation software. This procedure alone is therefore not sufficient, since it only prevents technical penetration.

At the same time, the actual 'data protection challenge' would be comparatively easy to solve, as it would be technically possible to anonymize personal fields (such as the username) in the intermediate step of a 'proxy software'. It is more difficult to prevent personal data in the text of the article. Although a scanner can be created that scans posts for personal data and filters them out, the effort involved would be high and a solution would probably have a high error rate. In addition, if it renders poor quality, the value of using the ESN would decrease substantially.

Furthermore, a mechanism would also be needed that makes it possible to send content back to the moderation software only on a given topic (in order to minimize the amount of text required). This means that an incoming request from the moderation software (i.e. from the Internet) opens a case. The answer to this case will be reported back to the Internet. If the case is closed, no further information goes outside. Other discussions that do not belong to the case are also not sent outside. Due to the case logic of the moderation software, the effort should be limited. However, not all ESN offer the necessary functions to support the case logic and would also have to be extended and users need training (Spiekermann, 2009).

6.3 Internal Installation

This would make it possible for the described solution to be installed internally. In addition to the comparatively high operating costs incurred by the constantly changing interfaces of the social media platforms, this would also only represent a comparatively limited solution to the problem, as ‘outside’ access to the other connected social media platforms would still be necessary. So the technical ‘vulnerability’ would not be completely eliminated. Neither does the accidental dissemination of internal data. This means that without an approach that limits the content that can actually be disseminated in some form (e.g. definition of specific groups), no advantage is achieved with regard to this risk by internal installation (Kietzmann, 2011).

6.4 Internet-Based Platform

In addition, the opposite case could also be a scenario. The provision of part of the internal community on the Internet, so that no interface between the intranet and the Internet would be necessary at all. This deployment makes sense in principle. However, if internal users have to switch to a special software/community in order to be able to answer requests from colleagues and clients, then the basic idea of the concept is called into question. This is actually the equivalent of a discussion in a customer forum, which can be achieved with less effort. In addition, it would also be conceivable to define different groups.

Appropriate rules of conduct could be defined for them. This would at least prevent internal discussions from easily reaching the outside world. But even this is more like a special customer forum and can be created with much less effort, but also does not cover the need for a tight integration of customer requests into internal communities (Treem, 2020).

6.5 Moderation

To prevent internal discussions from being disclosed externally, a moderator could also take on a controlling role (Ellison, 2024). However, the effort for this scenario seems very high and, in various practical applications, was discarded at an early stage.

7 Conclusions and Outlook

This article offers insights in the form of a point of view, based on results of an expert questionnaire and selected literature findings. In addition, in section 6, different technical solution scenarios were presented that take into consideration data protection challenges.

It becomes clear that the introduction of technical systems and solutions is never a purely technical matter. A wide variety of business areas must be involved, and different dimensions of the company must be taken into account. (Frommert, 2018). It was also shown that the challenges are not only the factual threat of potential data misuse, but also the emotional assessment by different parties hindered or made it difficult to find a solution at the technical level (Wehner, 2024).

Implementing ESN in the company is always a multidimensional project that must also be planned and implemented on a multidimensional level. Even if problems in the implementation appear to be of technical origin, the other areas of the organization must always be taken into account when analyzing the challenges. In addition to the technical implementation, the corporate culture must also be taken into account for the successful implementation of an ESN. Many companies initially shy away from the financial and organizational effort and thus hinder successful implementation (Hinchcliffe 2012). In

retrospect, however, the lack of investment is often regretted – there is a risk of losing competitiveness compared to companies that invested in this area at an early stage.

In conclusion, the value of ESN only materializes if all people embrace its possibilities, without risking infringing data privacy rules. The commitment to ESN and data protection not only creates modern and agile companies. In any sense, it can also be a driver for a company's ability to innovate and increase its social and economic relevance. ESN are not just a decorative plus that make companies more attractive to employees. It is a way that adapts work and communication processes in a global and digitalized world to social requirements and makes companies future-proof and sustainable.

As an indication for future research directions, the author suggests to further analyze the relevant factors for successful ESN implementation. This should help to provide a solid foundation for derivation of the design principles for the successful implementation of ESN in business and management. Also, future research should focus on the design of the guidelines for internal governance to fully comply with data protection regulation.

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